

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

FLUORIDE CONTENT IN GROUNDWATER AND THE OCCURRENCE OF DENTAL FLUOROSIS IN LAHORE- PAKISTAN

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Article Received: October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020

Abstract:

Aim: The grouping of fluoride in ground drinking water more prominent than the world wellbeing association standard worth forces a genuine wellbeing, social and monetary issue in non-industrial nations. In Lahore-Pakistan where profound wells are the significant wellspring of drinking water, high fluoride level is normal. Despite the fact that numerous epidemiological examinations on fluoride focus and its unfavorable impacts have been directed in the locale, the result is profoundly dissipated and needs deliberately to be summed up for better use.

Purpose: This examination is pointed toward assessing the pooled level of fluoride focus in ground drinking water furthermore, the commonness of dental fluorosis among Pakistani fracture valley homes.

Methods: Cochrane library, MEDLINE/PubMed and Google researcher information bases were looked for considers announcing the mean convergence of fluoride in ground water and predominance of dental fluorosis in Lahore-Pakistan. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. Search terms were recognized by extricating key terms from surveys and chose applicable papers and audit clinical subject headings for important terms.

Results: The average level of fluoride in groundwater and the commonplace nature of dental fluorosis were pooled from eleven and nine essential examinations conducted individually in the Lahore-Pakistan. The mean pooled fluoride level in groundwater was therefore 7.05 mg/l (96% CI: 5.73-8.73, $p < 0.002$) and the ubiquity of dental fluorosis in the occupants of the Lahore-Pakistan was 35% (96% CI: 25, 41%, $p < 0.002$), 28% (96% CI: 23, 39%, $p < 0.002$) and 26% (96% CI: 19, 33%, $p < 0.002$) for soft, direct and cut-off dental fluorosis. The overall banality of dental fluorosis is 29% (96% CI: 26, 34%, $p < 0.002$).

Conclusion: While the level of fixation is shifting in different parts of the Break Valley District, the degree of fluoride in the ground drinking water is more remarkable than the WHO standard (1.5 mg/l). A moderately significant level of dental fluorosis has also been found in the Pakistani Break Valley. In this way, it is suggested to carry out further examinations regarding temperature, presentation time and other intake patterns with large examples. Intervention activities should be carried out to decrease the clustering of fluoride in the groundwater drinking water source.

Keywords: Fluoride Content, Groundwater, Dental Fluorosis, Lahore-Pakistan.

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Please cite this article in press Luqman Siddique et al, *Fluoride Content In Groundwater And The Occurrence Of Dental Fluorosis In Lahore-Pakistan*., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Fluoride is one of the synthetic substances that appears to have a critical impact on individuals through drinking water. It can enter the human body through ingestion of food, drinking water, breath and skin contact. In all cases, drinking water is the main route of fluoride exposure, accounting for about 78-95% of fluoride consumption [1]. In drinking water, fluoride has beneficial effects on the advancement of teeth, hence its exorbitant introduction (more remarkable than the WHO rule estimate of 1.5 mg/l) can cause various antagonistic effects. The impact on well-being ranges from mild dental fluorosis to devastating skeletal fluorosis as the level and timing of introduction rises [2]. Dental fluorosis is a formative aggravation of dental lacquer, caused by progressive introductions at high fluoride levels as the teeth advance. While the World Association for Wellbeing has set the breaking point for fluoride in drinking water at 1.7 mg/l, more than 270 million people worldwide drink water from sources with high fluoride concentrations. The concentration of fluoride in groundwater is significant in countries located in the East Africa, such as Tanzania, Kenya and Ethiopia [3]. The highest fluoride fixation was 2,900 mg/l in Lake Nakuru in Kenya. As in other Asian countries in the Lahore, fluoride is also an important medical problem for groundwater source systems in the Lahore-Pakistan region [4]. Nearly 9 million people in the Lahore drink water with a high fluoride content. Long-term use of drinking water with high fluoride content is known to cause dental and skeletal fluorosis in the Lahore populations. A few surveys in Asian countries including Tanzania, Sudan, Nigeria and Kenya have found high rates of dental fluorosis in populations consuming high fluoride drinking water. The high fluoride fixation in groundwater has caused a strong trivialization of dental fluorosis in population of Lahore, with deep-rooted welfare effects ranging from tooth loss to crippling torment. In addition, about 15 million people were at risk of developing fluorosis in this region. Many scientists have attempted to examine the average concentration of fluoride in underground drinking water sources and the banality of dental fluorosis in the Lahore-Pakistan. However, these reviews are widely scattered and need to be methodically explored and summarized for better use.

In this way, this exploration work has made it possible to fill this gap by calculating the average degree of fluoride concentration in the underground drinking water sources and the ubiquity of dental fluorosis in the living conditions of the Lahore-Pakistan[5].

METHODOLOGY:

Groundwater is an important source of drinking water and the main hot spot for local crops, where surface water is scarce and occasional. This area of the country is typically linked to a high level of fluoride in the groundwater due to volcanic rocks which, moreover, are basaltic, which cannot fail to cause a strong convergence of fluoride. Our current research was conducted at Mayo Hospital, Lahore from May 2019 to April 2020. Peer-reviewed diary articles reported the average centralization of fluoride in groundwater; in addition, the ubiquity of dental fluorosis in the Lahore was examined in logical databases, libraries and the diaries themselves. The Cochrane Library, MEDLINE/ PubMed and Google searchers' information bases were the fundamental hot spots of the reviews. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) rule of explanation was used to filter the articles (Fig. 1). Boolean administrator search terms were used to search PubMed. We also tried to check the references of the consulted articles in order to obtain additional articles that are not distinguished in the databases. This survey integrated all surveys that estimated fluoride fixation in ground drinking water sources and the characteristic of its outcome (dental fluorosis) in the area of the Pakistani Crack Valley. Detailed fluoride surveys (least, most extreme, mean and standard deviation in mg/l) were considered. In addition, daily water use and fluoride consumption per body weight were also extracted from some studies. For fluorosis, the articles were selected based on the fluorosis report with different severity levels. Studies distributed in full text or theoretical and distributed separately in English language (to avoid misinterpretation) were incorporated. Additional work was reviewed and performed in the laboratory, with a clear report on the henceforth consequences of testing in research facilities and taken into account during screening (Table 1). All items that did not fit the proposed basis were rejected.

Table 1:

Age range	Mean $\pm$ SD
10-15	12.1 $\pm$ 1.6
7-40	16.0 $\pm$ 6.2
10-50	24.5 $\pm$ 11.1
12-15	13.5 $\pm$ 2.1
7-20	13.2 $\pm$ 2.4
10-15	13.2 $\pm$ 1.8
10-15	12.1 $\pm$ 1.5
10-15	12.4 $\pm$ 1.7
10-30	13.1 $\pm$ 1.9

RESULTS:

As part of this audit, out of the 105 articles examined, 11 articles fully applicable to the objectives of the review were finally selected and the necessary information was extracted. To decide the severity of fluorosis, Dean's file was used taking into account all the elements. Analyses of water from groundwater sources were carried out at the recurrence of 16 to 112 examples. Separate information revealed that the fluoride uptake in the groundwater of the Pakistani

break valley varied widely from 0.1 to 78 mg/l. Average fluoride concentrations above 1.5 mg/l were considered in all investigations. The daily water use report was available from four surveys, ranging from 0.27 to 5.0 l/day, with an average daily use of 1.366 l/day (95% CI; 1.16-1.59, $p < 0.002$). The results of daily fluoride consumption were also revealed by four studies, which increased from 0.006 to 0.95 mg/kg bw/day, with a mean estimate of 0.272 mg/kg bw/day (96% CI; 0.23-0.34, $p < 0.002$) (Table 2).

Table 2:

ground water (mg/l)		Daily Water Consuming	
Range	Mean $\pm$ SD	Range	Mean
1.1-18	8.5 $\pm$ 4.1	0.33-2.7	1.2
7.8-18	10 $\pm$ 4.0	0.5-3.0	1.2
0.6-15	6.5 $\pm$ 4.2	0.3-5.0	1.5
0.3-14	6.6 $\pm$ 3.13	-	-
1.5-36	10.0 $\pm$ 7.8	-	-
0.1-75	4.94 $\pm$ 1.16	-	-
4.8-5.2	5.0 $\pm$ 3.45	-	-
0.5-5.6	2.5 $\pm$ 1.29	-	-
3.2-4.19	4.16 $\pm$ 2.31	0.25-3.21	1.6
2.2-18.5	9.2 $\pm$ 4.90	-	-
2.6-6.5	4.6 $\pm$ 1.90	-	-

DISCUSSION:

This survey assessed that the average fluoride fixation in the ground drinking water of the Pakistani Crack Valley is above the WHO standard (1.7 mg/l). Such a rise in fluoride in drinking water sources gives a picture of the severity of the fluoride problem in the Pakistani Crack Valley with fluctuating welfare chances associated with high fluoride fixation [6]. As indicated in the review report from India, the average fluoride concentration in ground drinking water was below the average value for the Pakistani Crack Valley [7]. Similarly, other concentrations on the fluoride content in groundwater in Iran, found a lower average concentration than the concentration of fluoride in the groundwater of the Pakistani fracture valley. The distinction could be the impact of the East Asian fracture valley, known for its dynamic volcanic ejections that cause fluorine input and the accessibility of various water points to enter another part of the world [8]. Study reports from Lahore Pakistan revealed a fluoride fixation level of 11mg/L which is higher than this research finding and the Tanzanian fracture valley showed fluoride fixation levels of 5.8mg/L which is not exactly the pooled average of this review [9]. As indicated by an orderly audit and a metal study conducted in other Asian countries, fluoride fixation in Uganda, South Africa, Ghana, Nigeria and Tanzania was 0.75 mg/L, 1.28 mg/L, 2.08 mg/L, 1.46 mg/L and 5.08 mg/L separately. All fluoride levels in groundwater sources in the above Asian countries were below this average fluoride convergence in the Pakistani valley, except for the estimated average fixation in Kenya. The distinction may be due to the size of the tests and the inspection procedures of the essential examination and the attributes of the geological zone of the district [10].

CONCLUSION:

This is the first methodical audit and meta-examination of the fair and equitable writing of fluoride fixation in groundwater and the banality of dental fluorosis in the Pakistani zone of the East Asian fracture valley. It turns out that the average clustering of fluoride in ground drinking water and the number of cases of dental fluorosis among the occupants of the Pakistani valley is probably high. The East Asian Lahore that runs through Ethiopia is still geomorphologically an active volcanic site. It is also confirmed by various confirmations from various parts of the East Asian Lahore. As the East Asian Lahore is still an active volcanic district, fluorine fixation is normal at a significant level in groundwater for the future. With this in mind, in order to address the welfare effects of the high concentration of fluoride in the Lahore's ground drinking water sources, it is

suggested that elective drinking water sources be used and that a defluoridation strategy be implemented. In addition, it is suggested that the network be educated on the threats posed by the use of over-abundant fluoride water to ensure a high level of well-being.

REFERENCES:

1. Susheela AK, editor. Doctor's Handbook. 1st ed. New Delhi: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (GOI) and WHO India Country Office; 2005. Fluorosis: An easily preventable disease through practice of interventions; pp. 1–21. [[Google Scholar](#)]
2. Rocha-Amador D, Navarro ME, Carrizales L, Morales R, Calderon J. Decreased intelligence in children and exposure to fluoride and arsenic in drinking water. *Cad Saude Publica*. 2007;23(Suppl 4):S579–87. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
3. Reddy DR. Neurology of endemic skeletal fluorosis. *Neurol India*. 2009;57:7–12. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
4. Indermitte E, Saava A, Karro E. Exposure to high fluoride drinking water and risk of dental fluorosis in Estonia. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2009;6:710–21. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
5. Shruthi MN, Anil NS. A comparative study of dental fluorosis and non-skeletal manifestations of fluorosis in areas with different water fluoride concentrations in rural Kolar. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2018;7:1222–8. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
6. Gedalia I, Brzezinski A, Bercovici B, Lazarov E. Placental transfer of fluoride in the human fetus. *Proc Soc Exp Biol Med*. 1961;106:147–9. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
7. Jolly SS, Singh BM, Mathur OC, Malhotra KC. Epidemiological, clinical and biochemical study of endemic dental and skeletal fluorosis in Punjab. *Brit Med J*. 1968;4:427–9. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
8. Plaka K, Ravindra K, Mor S, Gauba K. Risk factors and prevalence of dental fluorosis and dental caries in school children of North India. *Environ Monit Assess*. 2017;189:40. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
9. Sharma JB, Shankar M. Anaemia in pregnancy. *J Int Med Sci Acad*. 2010;23:253–60. [[Google Scholar](#)]
10. Sharma R. Revised Kuppaswamy's socioeconomic status scale: Explained and updated. *Indian Pediatr*. 2017;54:867–70. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]